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AN ANALYSIS OF IMPACT RESISTANCE OF COMPOSITE BLADES FOR AIRCRAFT ENGINES
(ANALYSIS WITH TWO DIMENSIONAL AND THREE DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENTS)

Toshio Miyachi, Hidehito Okumura, Kunihiro Ohtake
National Aerospace Laboratory
Chofu-shi Jindaiji Higashi-machi 7-44-1, Tokyo Japan

ABSTRACT

An analysis has been conducted to determine the feasibility of composite fan blade for meeting impact resistance requirements for aircraft engines. Triangular plate elements were used in previous analysis ¹⁾. The results of the previous analysis agreed well with the experimental results for non-rotating blade. However, for rotating blades, no analysis nor experiment had been conducted. In this analysis, plate elements and three dimensional elements were used for finite element analysis and the effect of centrifugal force was taken into account. Impact response of six fan blade models were calculated. According to the results of the analysis with plate elements, the bending deformations are decreased significantly by centrifugal force. However, torsional deformations and local deformations are not significantly decreased. It seemed to indicate that the effect of centrifugal force on impact resistance of composite fan blade is not appreciable.

Beside the analysis with plate elements, an analysis with 3D (8-node brick-type) elements was conducted in order to evaluate out-of-plane stress in the blades. However, the results of vibrational analysis with 3D elements for a long, thin cantilever blade do not agree well with experimental results at present.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Fan Blades; Aircraft Engines; Impact Load;
Finite Element Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

If polymer matrix composites could be used for fan blades of aircraft turbofan engines, the weight of the engine would be reduced by 20% or more. However, because of poor impact resistance, polymer matrix composite has

not been applied for fan blade of aircraft engine yet. It is necessary to confirm the feasibility of polymer composite fan blade that the impact resistance is carefully evaluated.

It was confirmed in previous report that the analytical model and the method of analysis were valid for natural vibration and impact response of non-rotating fan blades ¹⁾. It is necessary to evaluate out-of-plane stress ²⁻³⁾ and the effect of centrifugal force for precise evaluation of impact resistance of fan blades. In this report, two dimensional (triangular plate) and three dimensional (8-node brick-type) elements were used for finite element analysis and the effect of centrifugal force was taken into account. Impact response of six blade models of different materials and sizes were calculated. Bending deformations are decreased by centrifugal force. However, torsional and local deformations were not appreciably decreased by centrifugal force, especially in the composite blades. And maximum strains in the blades were decreased only a little by centrifugal force. It seemed to indicate that the effect of centrifugal force on impact resistance of composite fan blades is not appreciable.

Since it is necessary to analyze three dimensional stress in the blade to evaluate impact resistance more precisely, finite element analysis with 3D elements has been conducted. But the results of the vibrational eigenvalue analysis with 8-node elements do not agree well with the experimental results for the blade model. It should be re-examined to apply the analysis with 8-node elements for long, thin, cantilever plate like fan blades.

Fig. 1 Blade Model and Impact Load

Table 1 Properties of Blade Materials

	Titanium Alloy	Carbon/Epoxy(Lamina)	SiC/Ti(Lamina)
EL(GPa)	116.1	132.6	200.7
ET(GPa)	116.1	10.20	162.2
GLT(GPa)	44.3	4.08	65.4
ν	0.31	0.26	0.24
ρ (kg/m ³)	4.52×10^3	1.53×10^3	3.85×10^3

Table 2 Characteristics of Blade Models

	Ti,1.0C	C/Ep,1.0C	1.65C/22°	1.65C/45°	2.06C/45°	SiC/Ti,1.0C
Material	Ti6Al4V	C/Epoxy	C/Epoxy	C/Epoxy	C/Epoxy	SiC/Ti
Chord(mm)	120	120	198	198	247	120
Size(ratio)	1.00	1.00	1.65	1.65	2.06	1.00
Lamination	Monolyt.	0 ± 22°	0 ± 22°	0 ± 45°	0 ± 45°	0 ± 22°

2. BLADE MODELS AND IMPACT LOAD

The models analyzed are simplified shape fan blades which simulate the fan blade of 50 kN (5 tons) thrust class turbo-fan engine. Original size model is shown in Fig. 1. Large cross section models which have 1.65 and 2.06 times chord length and thickness were also analyzed. Multiplier 1.65 and 2.06 are reciprocals of blade number in the fan disk, namely 33/20 and 33/16 which keep the aerodynamic similarity of the blading. Properties of materials and characteristics of analyzed models are shown in Tables 1 and 2. The models of composite blade are composed of 8 to 96 laminae according to thickness of each element. Impact load shown in Fig.1 is simulated load of 1.5 lb (680 g) bird strike which is one of the required tests for the engine airworthiness certification. Total momentum of impact is 15.85 Newton · Second for original size model. The momentum for large size models are multiplied by 1.65 or 2.06.

3. METHOD OF ANALYSIS

3.1 Impact Response The analytical model of the blade consists of 720 triangular flat plate elements with 403 nodes. Centrifugal force is assumed to be applied by 6000 rpm rotation around the axis perpendicular to the blade axis 300 mm distant from the blade fixed end. Newmark's beta method was used for the calculation. The time interval Δt for time integration is 2.5 or 5 μ s. Von Karman's plate theory was used for taking into account of geometrical nonlinearity for large deformation, but material nonlinearity was ignored in this analysis.

3.2 Natural Vibration Beside the same analytical model which was used for calculating the impact response, the model which consists of 1800 8-node brick-type elements with 3800 nodes was used for the analysis. Properties

of 8-node elements of composite blades were calculated by classical lamination theory. Subspace iteration method was used for the calculation.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Impact Response Deformed patterns of the blade models at 0 rpm and 6000 rpm at the instant the blade tip displacement reaches maximum are shown in Figs. 2 to 5. These figures show the deformed models looked from 45° direction to the blade chord line and 20° direction to the horizontal line, and the models looked vertically downward. Maximum tip displacement of titanium blade is decreased by about 60% by centrifugal force (Fig. 2). In carbon/epoxy and SiC/Ti blades, maximum tip displacements are decreased by about 40% by centrifugal force (Figs. 3 and 4). In 1.65 times large cross section carbon/epoxy, 0±45° ply blade, maximum tip displacement is decreased only a little by centrifugal force (Fig. 5). In the large cross section blade, deformation of blade chord line is remarkably increased.

Fig. 6 shows the time histories of principal strain of SiC/Ti blade at point S (See Fig. 1) at 0 rpm and 6000 rpm. Principal strain at point S is decreased to about 1/3 by centrifugal force. Point S is located on the center of convex surface, at the boundary of loaded and unloaded regeon of the blade. This point is selected for representing the time history of strain in the blade models, but strain at this point is not maximum in the blade. Fig. 7 shows principal strain distributions on the convex surface of SiC/Ti blade at 0 rpm and 6000 rpm at the instant the strain reaches maximum. The strain distribution is slightly changed by centrifugal force, but maximum strain in the blade generated by the impact is not decreased by

Fig. 2 Maximum Deformations of Titanium Blade Model

Fig. 3 Maximum Deformations of Composite Blade Model

Fig. 4 Maximum Deformations of SiC/Ti Blade Model

Fig. 5 Maximum Deformations of 1.65C/45° Composite Blade Model

Fig.6 Time Histories of Principal Strain at Point S on SiC/Ti Blade Model

Fig. 7 Strain Distributions in SiC/Ti Blade Model

Table 3 Maximum Principal Strain in Blade Models (%)

	Nrpm	Titanium	C/Ep,1.0C	1.65C/22°	1.65C/45°	2.06C/45°	SiC/Ti
ϵ	0	30.0	105.5	39.2	23.5	22.3	22.9
max.	6000	26.1	79.2	34.5	20.0	19.9	20.2

centrifugal force. The maximum strains of the blade models at 0 rpm and 6000 rpm are shown in Table 3. This table shows that maximum strains in the blade models are not appreciably decreased by centrifugal force, in spite of decreased global deformations. This is because local deformation is not affected by centrifugal force.

4.2 Natural Vibration Eigen frequencies of titanium and carbon/epoxy blade calculated with triangular plate elements and 8-node brick-type elements are shown in Table 4. Measured values for titanium blade are also shown in Table 4. Calculated eigen frequencies of titanium blade with plate elements agree well with measured values. Measured eigen modes of titanium blade are 1st bending, 2nd bending, 1st torsion and so on from the lowest to higher frequencies. Eigen frequencies of titanium blade calculated with 8-node elements are about 3 times larger than measured values and the order of eigen modes is different from measured order, namely 1st bending, 1st torsion, 2nd bending.

Table 4 Eigen Frequencies of Blade Models (Hz)

Finite Element	1st Bending		2nd Bending		1st Torsion	
	Plate	8-Node	Plate	8-Node	Plate	8-Node
Titanium	92.8	285	434	1345>	448	>1222
Ti(measured)		92		430		443
Carbon/Epoxy	150	425	676>	1883>	>412	>1096

Eigen modes of carbon/epoxy blade calculated with 8-node elements are shown in Fig. 8. These mode shapes correspond with those calculated with plate elements ¹⁾. However, calculated eigen frequencies of carbon/epoxy blade with 8-node elements are about 2.8 times larger than those calculated with plate elements. These discrepancies are considered to be generated from characteristics of 8-node elements which ignore bending (2nd and higher order) deformation. These results indicate the limit of applicability of 8-node elements for long, thin cantilever plate, such as fan blades.

For impact response analysis ⁴⁾, discrepancy will be smaller, since geometrical nonlinearity and material nonlinearity are taken into account. Geometrical nonlinearity allows rotation of elements and material nonlinearity gives more flexibility for large deformation. However, it is considered to be necessary to re-examine the application of 8-node brick-type elements for the analysis of long, thin plate such as fan blades.

Fig. 8 Eigen Modes of Composite Blade Model
Calculated with 8-Node Elements

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

1. Bending or global deformation of the fan blade model by the impact is decreased by centrifugal force, but local deformation is slightly affected by centrifugal force. Therefore, impact resistance of fan blade is considered to be affected only a little by centrifugal force.
2. There are big difference between eigen values calculated with triangular plate elements and 8-node brick-type elements. Eigen values calculated with plate elements agree well with measured values for the fan blade models. It is because of characteristics of 8-node element which ignores higher order deformation. It is necessary to re-examine the application of 8-node brick-type elements for the analysis of long, thin structures.

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Authors

Toshio Miyachi : Head of Compressor Laboratory, Aeroengine Division

Hidehito Okumura: Senior Researcher, Computational Sciences Division

Kunihiko Ohtake: Head of Thermostructure Laboratory, Structural Mechanics Division

National Aerospace Laboratory

Chofu-shi Jindaiji Higashi-machi 7-44-1, Tokyo Japan

Phone: (0422)47-5911(Ext. 441, 506, 474)

FAX : (0422)48-5888